

Treatment and Mortality Following Cancer Diagnosis Among People with Non-Affective Psychotic Disorders in Ontario, Canada: A Retrospective Cohort Study

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Abstract

Background and Hypothesis: People with psychotic disorders have a higher risk of mortality following cancer diagnosis, compared to people without psychosis. The extent to which this disparity is influenced by differences in cancer-related treatment is currently unknown. We hypothesized that, following a cancer diagnosis, people with psychotic disorders were less likely to receive treatment and were at higher risk of death than those without psychosis.

Study Design: We constructed a retrospective cohort of cases of non-affective psychotic disorder (NAPD) and a general population comparison group, using Ontario health administrative data. We identified cases of all cancers diagnosed between 1995 and 2019 and obtained information on cancer-related treatment and mortality. Cox proportional hazards models were used to compare the probability of having a consultation with an oncologist and receiving cancer-related treatment, adjusting for tumor site and stage. We also compared the rate of all-cause and cancer-related mortality between the two groups, adjusting for tumor site.

Study Results: Our analytic sample included 24,944 people diagnosed with any cancer. People with NAPD were less likely to receive treatment **than people without psychosis** (HR=0.87,95%CI=0.82,0.91). In addition, people with NAPD had a greater risk of death from any cause (HR=1.68,95%CI=1.60,1.76), compared to people without NAPD.

Conclusions: The lower likelihood of receiving cancer treatment reflects disparities in accessing cancer care for people with psychotic disorders, which may partially explain the higher mortality risk following cancer diagnosis. Future research should explore mediating factors in this relationship to identify targets for reducing health disparities.

Keywords: psychosis, schizophrenia, oncology, cancer care, health disparities

1 Introduction

People with psychotic disorders suffer from higher mortality rates compared to the general population, with a higher incidence of physical comorbidities accounting for the majority of this gap.¹ Due to a variety of patient, provider, and health system factors, people with severe psychiatric illnesses are also less likely to receive guideline-recommended treatment for chronic health conditions, including cancer.^{2,3} Previous research has found that people with pre-existing mental disorders have a higher risk of all-cause and cancer-related mortality following a diagnosis of cancer, compared to people without mental disorders.²

In a previous study, we found that people with non-affective psychotic disorders (NAPD) had a higher incidence of cancer compared to people without NAPD, with substantial heterogeneity by primary tumor location.⁴ In addition, we found that people with NAPD had greater odds of more advanced stage cancer at diagnosis, compared to people without NAPD, indicating a delay in diagnosis.⁴ This likely contributes to these health disparities experienced by people with psychosis.⁴ Prior literature has seldom examined all aspects of cancer care within a single cohort, including cancer incidence, stage at diagnosis, treatment, and mortality. The present study continues our examination, employing large-scale population-based health administrative data to explore disparities across the cancer care continuum for people with NAPD in Ontario, Canada. In Canada, healthcare is publicly funded, thereby limiting barriers associated with cost of healthcare.

Our objectives were: (1) to compare probabilities of receiving treatment and consultation with an oncologist among people with NAPD, relative to those without; and (2) to compare all-cause and cancer-related mortality following cancer diagnosis among people with NAPD, relative to those without. We hypothesized that following cancer diagnosis, people with NAPD would be less likely to receive consultation and treatment and to suffer greater mortality risk, compared to people without NAPD.

2 Methods

2.1 Study Design and Data Sources

We conducted a retrospective cohort study using population-based health administrative data from Ontario, Canada. We used health administrative databases from ICES, which contain information on hospital admissions, emergency department visits, outpatient physician billings, and data on characteristics of patients and physicians. Databases were linked at the patient level using unique, encoded identifiers, and analyzed at ICES. The use of the data in this project is authorized under section 45 of Ontario's Personal Health Information Protection Act (PHIPA) and does not require review by a Research Ethics Board. A description of the databases used in this study can be found in Supplemental Table 1. This manuscript followed the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guidelines,⁵ available in Supplemental Table 2.

2.2 Cohort Creation

The creation of the study cohort has been described in detail previously.⁴ We identified people aged 14 to 59 with a first diagnosis of NAPD, including schizophrenia spectrum disorder and psychosis not otherwise specified (NOS), between January 1995 and December 2004 using a validated algorithm (Table 1).⁶ Affective psychoses were not included, as they cannot be reliably identified in outpatient billings. We looked back five years prior to the first diagnosis of NAPD to exclude prevalent cases of NAPD. A comparison group of people without NAPD were randomly sampled from the general population. People younger than 14 at the index date were excluded, due to low incidence of both psychosis and cancer in this age group, and those over 60 were excluded to avoid misdiagnosed cases of dementia. To ensure adequate follow-up and data completeness, non-residents of Ontario and those who were ineligible for the Ontario Health Insurance Plan (OHIP) one year prior to cohort entry were excluded. People with prior cancer diagnoses were also excluded.

The analytic sample for the current study includes all people with an incident cancer diagnosis following cohort entry, as identified using the Ontario Cancer Registry (OCR).⁷ The cohort was followed from the date of cancer diagnosis until December 31st, 2019 to ascertain outcomes. We excluded anyone with missing data on neighbourhood-level income, rurality of residence, or access to a family physician at the time of cancer diagnosis.

2.3 Outcomes

Consultation with an oncologist was defined as the first consultation with a medical oncologist following cancer diagnosis. Receipt of cancer treatment was defined as the first receipt of either surgery, chemotherapy, or radiotherapy following cancer diagnosis. We also examined the receipt of each treatment modality following cancer diagnosis. Surgeries and consultations with an oncologist were identified through physician billings, visits to ambulatory care, and hospital discharges. Radiotherapy and chemotherapy were also identified from these databases, in addition to the Activity Level Reporting (ALR) database, which contains billings for all cancer-related care in Ontario (radiotherapy: sensitivity=92.0%, specificity=99.3%; chemotherapy: sensitivity=77.7%, specificity=99.2%).⁸ Radiotherapy and chemotherapy were also defined using a secondary algorithm for use in sensitivity analysis, relying solely on physician billings and hospital discharges, because the ALR was only available after 2004 (Supplemental Table 3). We recorded the time from the date of cancer diagnosis to the earliest billing date for each event.

The mortality outcomes were defined as the person-time from the date of cancer diagnosis to all-cause and cancer-related death. Mortality data were obtained from the Registered Persons Database (RPDB), which contains sociodemographic data for all Ontario residents.⁹ Cause of death data were obtained from the OCR; however, these data were only available up to 2014.

2.4 Covariates

We obtained information on several potential confounding variables at the date of cancer diagnosis. Age and sex were defined as continuous and binary variables, respectively. Neighborhood-level income quintile was assigned based on the census data for each postal code. The rurality index of Ontario was used to identify rural residences, defined as communities above the 40th percentile. Access to a family physician was defined based on whether each person was assigned to a family physician at the time of cancer diagnosis. Comorbidities at the time of cancer diagnosis were measured using the John Hopkins aggregated diagnostic groups (ADG) algorithm, a validated proprietary algorithm which used data from prior OHIP and hospital discharge billings to group diagnoses based on duration, severity, diagnostic certainty, etiology, and specialty care involvement.¹⁰

Cancer site was based on International Classification of Diseases for Oncology (3rd Edition) topography codes for the primary tumor site. Cancer stage at diagnosis was classified using the tumour, node, and metastases American Joint Classification of Cancer Staging criteria for the primary tumour site. The cohort was followed until death, a new onset of NAPD in the comparison group, or the end of the follow-up period (December 2019), at which point observations were censored.

2.5 Analyses

Descriptive characteristics of the cohort were summarized using frequencies, proportions, and standardized differences. Significant between-group differences were indicated by standardized differences greater than 10%.¹¹

Cox proportional hazards models were used to compare the probability of having a consultation with an oncologist and treatment following cancer diagnosis, between people with NAPD and those without. We adjusted for age, sex, neighbourhood-level income quintile, rurality of residence, access to a family physician, primary tumour location, stage at diagnosis, and comorbidities. We also used Cox

models to individually compare probability of surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy between people with NAPD and those without, adjusting for the same covariates. For each treatment-related outcome, the observation-time was censored if the person died, if they reached the maximum follow-up (31-December-2019) without the outcome occurring, or if a person in the comparison group had a new onset of NAPD within the period.

Cox proportional hazards models were used to compare all-cause mortality rates following cancer diagnosis between people with NAPD and people without NAPD. We adjusted for age, sex, neighbourhood-level income quintile, rurality of residence, access to a family physician, and comorbidities. Stage at diagnosis and treatment variables were not included in the models of mortality, as these are mediator variables that are on the causal pathway (see figure 1).¹² Cause-specific Cox models were used to compare cancer-specific mortality rates following cancer diagnosis between people with NAPD and people without NAPD, adjusting for the same covariates. Cause of death was only available for deaths that occurred prior to 2014; therefore, all models of cause-specific mortality are restricted to this period. We used another cause-specific Cox model to assess the threat of competing risks due to non-cancer-related death, following cancer diagnosis. Cause-specific Cox models were selected over sub-distribution hazards models for ease of interpretability.¹³ Follow-up time was censored if the person survived until the end of the follow-up period (31-December-2019) or if that person was in the comparison group and had a new onset of NAPD. In the cause-specific hazards models, deaths from other causes were censored.

Both models of receipt of treatment and mortality were stratified post-hoc by primary tumour location to examine heterogeneity in receipt of treatment, as this informs treatment decisions by clinicians. Furthermore, in our previous analysis,⁴ sex was found to be a significant effect modifier of cancer incidence among people with psychotic disorders and expect these differences to carry through the cancer care continuum. Therefore, we also performed post-hoc sex-stratified analyses.

We also conducted several sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of our findings to data quality issues and other methodological decisions. Sensitivity analyses were also performed by stratifying treatment models by solid versus non-solid tumours. Sensitivity analyses were performed to determine the effect of using the alternate definitions for chemotherapy and radiotherapy, and restricting to cancer diagnoses before 2005, which is the earliest date when oncology clinic claims are available. We also used Fine-gray sub distribution hazards models comparing consultation with an oncologist and receipt of treatment, adjusting for the competing risk of death and all other covariates.¹⁴

All statistical analyses were performed using STATA v16, and results are presented as hazard ratios (HR) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CI).

3 Results

3.1 Cohort

The characteristics of the analytic sample are described in Table 2. During the observation period, 5,002 and 19,940 cases of cancer were identified among people diagnosed with NAPD and the comparison group, respectively. The mean age at cancer diagnosis was 56.8 years (SD=10.4) for people with NAPD and 57.6 years (SD=10.6) for the comparison group. A larger proportion of people with NAPD were female (56.8% versus 52.0%) and in the lowest quintile for neighbourhood-level income (34.9% vs. 17.9%). People with NAPD were also more likely to reside in an urban area at the time of cancer diagnosis (90.6% versus 86.3%). Similar proportions of people with NAPD and the comparison group had access to a family physician at the time of cancer diagnosis (93.9% and 95.2%, respectively).

3.2 Consultation and Cancer Treatment

Among those who had a consultation with an oncologist, the median time from cancer diagnosis to the first consultation was 56 days. Among those who received any treatment, the median time from cancer

diagnosis to the first treatment was 40 days. The results of the Cox proportional hazards models for consultation and cancer treatment following cancer diagnosis can be found in Table 3. Following a cancer diagnosis, people with NAPD had a slightly lower likelihood of having a consultation with an oncologist compared to people without NAPD, adjusting for age, sex, neighbourhood-level income quintile, rurality of residence, access to a family physician, primary tumour location, and comorbidities (HR=0.92, 95%CI=0.88,0.96). People with NAPD were also 13% less likely than people without NAPD to receive any treatment following cancer diagnosis adjusting for all covariates (HR=0.87, 95%CI=0.82,0.91). Specifically, people with NAPD had a lower probability of receiving surgery (HR=0.94, 95%CI=0.89,0.98), chemotherapy (HR=0.80, 95%CI=0.76,0.84), and radiotherapy (HR=0.87, 95%CI=0.82,0.91) following cancer diagnosis, compared to people without NAPD, adjusting for all covariates.

The results of the Cox models for consultation with an oncologist and any treatment, stratified by primary tumour location, can be found in Supplemental Table 4. Compared to people without NAPD, people with NAPD had a particularly lower likelihood of having a consultation with an oncologist, following diagnosis with oral cancer (HR=0.68, 95%CI=0.51,0.92) and pancreatic cancer (HR=0.67, 95%CI=0.47,0.94); but had a greater probability of having consultation with an oncologist following diagnosis with uterine cancer (HR=1.74, 95%CI=1.24,2.43). Compared to people without NAPD, people with NAPD had a particularly lower probability of receiving any treatment following diagnosis with pancreatic cancer (HR=0.49, 95%CI=0.28,0.88) and prostate cancer (HR=0.66, 95%CI=0.54,0.81); but had a greater probability of receiving treatment following diagnosis with melanoma (HR=1.79, 95%CI=1.24,2.60).

The results of the post-hoc sex-stratified analyses can be found in Supplemental Table 5. Sex was found to be an effect modifier of the association between having NAPD and probability of receiving consultation with an oncologist and treatment following cancer diagnosis. Males with NAPD were less

likely to receive consultation with an oncologist and less likely to receive any treatment, compared to males without NAPD.

Diagnosis with solid versus non-solid tumours was not found to be a significant effect modifier of the association between having NAPD and a lower likelihood of receiving treatment (Supplemental Table 6). However, for individual treatment modalities, the effect of having NAPD on likelihood of receiving chemotherapy and radiotherapy was more pronounced among those diagnosed with non-solid tumours, compared to those with solid tumours.

Accounting for death as a competing risk did not significantly alter results (Supplemental Table 7). Using the alternate definitions to identify chemotherapy and radiotherapy did not significantly influence the results (Supplemental Table 3). In the comparison group, the follow-up time of 93 people (0.5%) were censored due to new onset of a psychotic disorder. Excluding these people did not change the findings.

3.3 Mortality

Among those who died during the follow-up period, the median time to death from cancer diagnosis was 484 days. The Kaplan Meier survival curves from the date of cancer diagnosis to death from any cause are displayed in Figure 2. In both groups, there was a relatively steep decline in survival probability within the first 5 years, after which survival probability declines steadily. This initial decline in survival probability following cancer diagnosis was much steeper among people with NAPD. At every time point following cancer diagnosis, people with NAPD had a significantly lower survival probability, compared to people without NAPD.

The results of the Cox proportional hazards models for all-cause mortality and cancer-related mortality can be found in Table 3. People with NAPD had a 61% greater risk of death from any cause (HR=1.61, 95%CI=1.54,1.69) following cancer diagnosis, compared to people without NAPD, adjusting for age, sex, income quintile, access to a family physician, rurality of residence, and comorbidities.

People with NAPD also had a 54% greater risk of cancer-related death compared to people without NAPD (HR=1.54, 95%CI=1.45,1.65), among those who had not yet experienced a mortality event, adjusting for all covariates.

The results of the Cox proportional hazards models for all-cause mortality and cancer-related mortality stratified by primary tumour location can be found in Table 3. Compared to people without NAPD, people with NAPD had a particularly higher risk of death from any cause, following diagnosis with breast cancer (HR=2.07, 95%CI=1.81,2.37), laryngeal cancer (HR=4.99, 95%CI=2.73,9.15), melanoma (HR=2.73, 95%CI=1.94,3.85), and prostate cancer (HR=2.30, 95%CI=1.83,2.89).

There was a small but non-significant sex difference in the effect of having NAPD on all-cause and cancer-specific mortality following cancer diagnosis (Supplemental Table 5). In the comparison group, the follow-up time of 140 people (0.7%) were censored due to new onset of a psychotic disorder. Excluding these people did not change the findings.

4 Discussion

Our study is one of few to perform a comprehensive longitudinal examination of disparities faced by people with psychosis across the cancer care continuum, showing lower likelihood of treatment and greater risk of mortality among people with NAPD compared to people without. Our findings are strengthened by the use of a large representative sample, long follow-up period, and population-based health administrative data in a country with universal health care.

In our previous study using the same cohort, we identified an elevated overall cancer incidence and a greater odds of advanced stage at diagnosis among people with NAPD, indicative of a diagnostic delay, which is also supported by other literature.^{4,15} This diagnostic delay is likely the result of poor screening uptake among people with psychosis.¹⁶ Owens and colleagues identified several barriers to accessing breast and cervical cancer screening procedures among women with mental illness, including

difficulty obtaining transportation, fear of stigma, adverse experiences, lack of reminders, and discomfort with healthcare providers.^{17,18} ‘Diagnostic overshadowing,’ or the misattribution of symptoms of other medical illnesses to underlying psychiatric illnesses, likely also contributes to this delay.¹⁹ Furthermore, people with NAPD have greater odds of having missing data for stage at diagnosis, suggestive of a lack of information pertinent to treatment and prognosis, which may affect quality of care.^{4,20}

In agreement with previous literature, the present analysis found that people with psychotic disorders were slightly less likely to have a consultation with an oncologist and treatment following a cancer diagnosis, compared to people without NAPD. A meta-analysis by Kisely et al.²¹ found that people with severe mental illness had longer wait times and were less likely to receive guideline-appropriate treatment for breast cancer, but did not find differences in receiving individual interventions, citing inadequate adjustment for confounding among included studies. In our analyses of time to treatment, we found a lower likelihood of receiving surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy. These effects were even more pronounced in our *post-hoc* sensitivity analysis, which accounted for death as a competing risk, suggesting that people with NAPD are dying before having a chance to receive treatment, highlighting the importance of timely care following a cancer diagnosis.^{22,23} Differences in receipt of treatment are likely mediated by biases in treatment decisions by physicians, as well as behavioural factors related to psychosis. Cognitive and perceptual impairments associated with psychosis may limit someone’s ability to adhere to treatment regimens and seek care.²¹ Similar disparities in treatment have also been observed for cardiovascular disease, as patients with mental illnesses are less likely to undergo revascularization procedures, which persisted despite similar severity of cardiovascular disease.^{3,24}

We also identified significant effect modification by sex on the probability of receiving treatment, adjusting for primary tumour location, stage at diagnosis, and other covariates. Adjusting for primary tumour location should account for differences in the treatment of different cancers, as the risk of being diagnosed with different cancers varies between sexes, e.g., sex-specific cancers. This may be attributable

to sex and gender differences in psychosis by sex where, on average, males with psychosis experience more severe negative symptoms, lower functioning, and have a higher prevalence of substance use issues, compared to females with psychosis.²⁵ Therefore, females with psychosis may have better adherence to treatment, or be perceived to adhere better by clinicians.

We also found that people with NAPD had a higher risk of all-cause and cancer-related mortality following cancer diagnosis, compared to people without NAPD. It is important to note that these differences exist with only a slightly elevated incidence of cancer overall among people with NAPD (IRR=1.09, 95%CI=1.05,1.12), reflecting a compounding of health inequalities.⁴ Our findings are consistent with prior literature showing that people with psychotic disorders have poorer outcomes and higher mortality following cancer diagnosis, compared to those without.^{2,12} Compared to the two prior meta-analyses on this topic,^{12,26} our study produced a slightly larger HR for all-cause mortality; however, these meta-analyses included several studies which over-adjusted for causal pathway variables, which likely attenuated the pooled effect.^{12,26}

We hypothesize that heterogeneity in mortality risk for people with NAPD by primary tumour location may be related to the complexity of treatment regimens and lower treatment initiation or adherence among people with psychosis. Analyses of routes to cancer diagnosis have found that people with psychotic disorders are more likely to be diagnosed with cancer following presentation to the emergency department, which is associated with later stage at diagnosis and worse mortality risk following a cancer diagnosis.²⁷

In agreement with previous studies, our stratified analyses found especially high excess mortality for people with NAPD following diagnosis with melanoma, laryngeal cancer, prostate cancer, and testicular cancer.^{12,26} Recommended first-line treatment for many of these cancers, such as radiotherapy may require consistent clinic visits or adherence to oral medications, which may be difficult to adhere to for people with complex mental health issues, consequently worsening mortality risk,²⁸ even among those

who are provided treatment. This also contributes to a phenomenon known as ‘therapeutic nihilism,’ whereby people with severe mental illnesses are less likely to receive treatment due to the perceived inability to adhere to complex treatment regimens.¹⁹ This may be further evidenced by the greater disparity in receipt of chemotherapy and radiotherapy versus surgery, between people with NAPD and people without.

The disparity in receipt of chemotherapy and radiotherapy among people with NAPD relative to people without was even more pronounced among those diagnosed with non-solid tumours, compared to solid tumours. Treatment of non-solid hematologic malignancies frequently involves complex treatment regimens including high dose chemotherapy or autologous or allogenic stem cell transplants, which carry very high safety risks.²⁹ As such, oncologists may be less likely to offer these treatments to patients suffering from severe mental illnesses, such as psychosis.

Previous research using data from SEER-Medicare suggests that people with pre-existing mental illness have lower rates of initiation, adherence, and continuation of endocrine therapy for breast cancer.³⁰ People with mental illness also have a higher risk of adverse post-operative outcomes, compared to people without mental illness, which may further reduce their likelihood of candidacy for surgical procedures.^{31,32} There may also be concern among physicians regarding treatment safety and monitoring as an outpatient, as people with mental illness may be less likely to access care for complications or side effects.

Previous research also suggests that concurrent medical illness (such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and obesity),³³ advanced stage at diagnosis, and differences in likelihood of receiving treatment and delivery of care are likely the primary mediating factors for the higher mortality risk following cancer diagnosis among people with psychotic disorders.¹² People with psychotic disorders are more likely to engage in lifestyle behaviours, such as smoking, sedentary lifestyle, and poor diet, which contribute to morbidity of concurrent medical illnesses and worse survival. Others have also suggested that the higher

mortality risk following cancer diagnosis is partially attributable to higher rates of death by suicide among people with psychotic disorders;² however, there is little evidence to support this.

4.1 Limitations

Our study is limited by the billing data available in administrative databases held by ICES. As such, we are only able to determine which treatments were undertaken, rather than which modalities were offered. Furthermore, we are unable to adjust for several important confounding variables, such as smoking behaviours. The case definition for NAPD has a high sensitivity and low specificity,⁶ which may have misclassified some people as having NAPD, however this is expected to be nondifferential. Furthermore, we are unable to identify affective psychoses within the health administrative data due to a lack of specificity in outpatient billing codes; therefore, our results may not be generalizable to people diagnosed with bipolar disorder or major depressive disorder with psychotic features. Additionally, these findings may not be generalizable to countries without publicly funded healthcare.

Cause of death data were only available prior to 2014. Therefore, our findings regarding cancer-related mortality are restricted to those who died prior to 2014 and may not be generalizable to mortality events after this period. In addition, the most recent validation of cancer-related death classifications in Ontario health administrative was conducted in 2006.³⁴ Furthermore, this shorter window may have truncated follow-up times for analyses of cancer-related mortality, relative to that of all-cause mortality.

Neighbourhood-level income was only measured during census years, and we are unable to account for movement between areas across census intervals. Neighbourhood-level income may also serve as a poor proxy for individual-level income.³⁵ Therefore, there may be some misclassification of income in our cohort.

4.2 Conclusions

These findings highlight the need for better integration and continuity of care across specialties to improve the quality of cancer care for people with psychotic disorders. In addition, efforts should be made to improve support and access to care, as well as ensuring that people with psychotic disorders receive timely and adequate treatment for cancer. Future research should identify specific patient, provider, and health system barriers to accessing cancer treatment among people with psychosis. In addition, further investigation is required to elucidate the mediating role of later stage at diagnosis, comorbidities, and treatment disparities in mortality risk among people with psychosis following cancer diagnosis. Identifying the contribution of these factors will identify critical points of intervention in the cancer care continuum.

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ICES is an independent, non-profit research institute whose legal status under Ontario's health information privacy law allows it to collect and analyze health care and demographic data, without consent, for health system evaluation and improvement. Secure access to these data is governed by policies and procedures that are approved by the Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario. The dataset from this study will be held securely in coded form at ICES and an analyst will have full access to study data. While data sharing agreements prohibit ICES from making the dataset publicly available, access can

be granted to those who meet pre-specified criteria for confidential access. The full dataset creation plan is available upon request.

This document used data adapted from the Statistics Canada Postal Code^{OM} Conversion File, which is based on data licensed from Canada Post Corporation, and/or data adapted from the Ontario Ministry of Health Postal Code Conversion File, which contains data copied under license from ©Canada Post Corporation and Statistics Canada. Parts of this material are based on data and/or information compiled and provided by the Canadian Institute for Health Information (CIHI), Ontario Ministry of Health (MOH), Ontario Health (OH), and Cancer Care Ontario (CCO). The analyses, conclusions, opinions, and statements expressed herein are those of the authors and do not reflect those of the funding or data sources; no endorsement is intended or should be inferred. All authors report no conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

6 Data availability statement

The dataset from this study is held securely in coded form at ICES. While legal data sharing agreements between ICES and data providers (e.g., healthcare organizations and government) prohibit ICES from making the dataset publicly available, access may be granted to those who meet pre-specified criteria for confidential access, available at www.ices.on.ca/DAS (email: das@ices.on.ca). The full dataset creation plan and underlying analytic code are available from the authors upon request, understanding that the computer programs may rely upon coding templates or macros that are unique to ICES and are therefore either inaccessible or may require modification.

7 References

1. Parks J, Svendsen D, Singer P, Foti ME. *Morbidity and Mortality in People with Serious Mental Illness.*; 2006.
2. Mahar AL, Kurdyak P, Hanna TP, Coburn NG, Groome PA. The effect of a severe psychiatric illness on colorectal cancer treatment and survival: A population-based retrospective cohort study. *PLoS One.* 2020;15(7 July):e0235409.
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0235409
3. Druss BG, Bradford DW, Rosenheck RA, Radford MJ, Krumholz HM. Mental disorders and use of cardiovascular procedures after myocardial infarction. *J Am Med Assoc.* 2000;283(4):506-511. doi:10.1001/jama.283.4.506
4. Wootten JC, Richard L, Blanchette PSP, Wiener JC, Anderson KK. Cancer incidence and stage at diagnosis among people with recent-onset psychotic disorders: A retrospective cohort study using Ontario health administrative data. *Psychooncology.* 2022;31(9):1510-1518. doi:10.1002/pon.5983
5. von Elm E, Altman DG, Egger M, Pocock SJ, Gøtzsche PC, Vandenbroucke JP. The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. *Lancet.* 2007;370(9596):1453-1457. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(07)61602-X
6. Kurdyak P, Lin E, Green D, Vigod S. Validation of a population-based algorithm to detect chronic psychotic illness. *Canadian Journal of Psychiatry.* 2015;60(8):362-368.
doi:10.1177/070674371506000805
7. Proadhan S, King MJ, De P, Gilbert J. Health Services Data: The Ontario Cancer Registry (a Unique, Linked, and Automated Population-Based Registry). In: Sobolev B, Levy A,

- Goring S, eds. *Data and Measures in Health Services Research*. Springer US; 2016:1-28.
doi:10.1007/978-1-4899-7673-4_18-2
8. Weerasinghe A, Smith CR, Majpruz V, et al. Validity of Administrative Databases in Comparison to Medical Charts for Breast Cancer Treatment Data. *J Cancer Epidemiol*. 2018;2018:12. doi:10.1155/2018/9218595
 9. Ontario Ministry of Health and Long Term Care. *Health Analyst's Toolkit*.; 2012.
 10. Austin PC, Van Walraven C, Wodchis WP, Newman A, Anderson GM. Using the Johns Hopkins Aggregated Diagnosis Groups (ADGs) to predict mortality in a general adult population cohort in Ontario, Canada. *Med Care*. 2011;49(10):932.
doi:10.1097/MLR.0B013E318215D5E2
 11. Austin PC. Using the standardized difference to compare the prevalence of a binary variable between two groups in observational research. *Commun Stat Simul Comput*. 2009;38(6):1228-1234. doi:10.1080/03610910902859574
 12. Davis LE, Bogner E, Coburn NG, et al. Stage at diagnosis and survival in patients with cancer and a pre-existing mental illness: A meta-analysis. *J Epidemiol Community Health (1978)*. 2020;74(1):84-94. doi:10.1136/jech-2019-212311
 13. Austin PC, Fine JP. Practical recommendations for reporting Fine-Gray model analyses for competing risk data. Published online 2017. doi:10.1002/sim.7501
 14. Fine JP, Gray RJ. A Proportional Hazards Model for the Subdistribution of a Competing Risk. *J Am Stat Assoc*. 1999;94(446):496-509. doi:10.1080/01621459.1999.10474144
 15. Wootten JC, Wiener JC, Blanchette P, Anderson KK. Cancer Incidence among People with Psychotic Disorders: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Psychooncology*. Published online 2022:1-9. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/pon.5983>

16. Solmi M, Firth J, Miola A, et al. Disparities in cancer screening in people with mental illness across the world versus the general population: prevalence and comparative meta-analysis including 4 717 839 people. *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2020;7(1):52-63. doi:10.1016/S2215-0366(19)30414-6
17. Owen C, Jessie D, De Vries Robbe M. Barriers to cancer screening amongst women with mental health problems. *Health Care Women Int*. 2002;23(6-7):561-566. doi:10.1080/07399330290107322
18. Aggarwal A, Pandurangi A, Smith W. Disparities in breast and cervical cancer screening in women with mental illness: A systematic literature review. *Am J Prev Med*. 2013;44(4):392-398. doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2012.12.006
19. Viron MJ, Stern TA. The Impact of Serious Mental Illness on Health and Healthcare. *Psychosomatics*. 2010;51(6):458-465. doi:10.1016/S0033-3182(10)70737-4
20. Mahar AL, Kurdyak P, Hanna TP, Coburn NG, Groome PA. Cancer staging in individuals with a severe psychiatric illness: A cross-sectional study using population-based cancer registry data. *BMC Cancer*. 2020;20(1). doi:10.1186/s12885-020-06943-w
21. Kisely S, Alotiby MKN, Protani MM, Soole R, Arnautovska U, Siskind D. Breast cancer treatment disparities in patients with severe mental illness: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychooncology*. Published online March 14, 2023. doi:10.1002/PON.6120
22. Berry SD, Ngo L, Samelson EJ, Kiel DP. Competing Risk of Death: An Important Consideration in Studies of Older Adults. *J Am Geriatr Soc*. 2010;58(4):783. doi:10.1111/J.1532-5415.2010.02767.X
23. Buzkova P. Competing risk of mortality in association studies of non-fatal events. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(8):e0255313. doi:10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0255313

24. Lawrence DM, Holman CDAJ, Jablensky A V., Hobbs MST. Death rate from ischaemic heart disease in Western Australian psychiatric patients 1980-1998. 2003;182(JAN.):31-36. Accessed June 8, 2021. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12509315/>
25. Carter B, Wootten J, Archie S, Terry AL, Anderson KK. Sex and gender differences in symptoms of early psychosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Archives of Women's Mental Health* 2022. 2022;1:1-13. doi:10.1007/S00737-022-01247-3
26. Zhuo C, Tao R, Jiang R, Lin X, Shao M. Cancer mortality in patients with schizophrenia: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *British Journal of Psychiatry*. 2017;211(1):7-13. doi:10.1192/bjp.bp.116.195776
27. Flytkjaer Virgilsen L, Falborg AZ, Vedsted P, Prior A, Pedersen AF, Jensen H. Unplanned cancer presentation in patients with psychiatric disorders: A nationwide register-based cohort study in Denmark. *Cancer Epidemiol*. 2022;81:102293. doi:10.1016/j.canep.2022.102293
28. Hershman DL, Shao T, Kushi LH, et al. Early discontinuation and non-adherence to adjuvant hormonal therapy are associated with increased mortality in women with breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Res Treat*. 2011;126(2):529-537. doi:10.1007/S10549-010-1132-4/FIGURES/2
29. Sochacka-ćwikła A, Mączyński M, Regiec A. FDA-Approved Drugs for Hematological Malignancies—The Last Decade Review. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2022;14(1). doi:10.3390/CANCERS14010087
30. Haskins CB, McDowell BD, Carnahan RM, et al. Impact of preexisting mental illness on breast cancer endocrine therapy adherence. *Breast Cancer Res Treat*. 2019;174(1):197-208. doi:10.1007/S10549-018-5050-1/FIGURES/2

31. Chou FHC, Tsai KY, Su CY, Lee CC. The incidence and relative risk factors for developing cancer among patients with schizophrenia: A nine-year follow-up study. *Schizophr Res.* 2011;129(2-3):97-103. doi:10.1016/j.schres.2011.02.018
32. McBride KE, Solomon MJ, Bannon PG, Glozier N, Steffens D. Surgical outcomes for people with serious mental illness are poorer than for other patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medical Journal of Australia.* 2021;214(8):379-385. doi:10.5694/MJA2.51009
33. Onitilo AA, Engel JM, Glurich I, Stankowski R V, Williams GM, Doi SA. Diabetes and cancer I: risk, survival, and implications for screening. doi:10.1007/s10552-012-9972-3
34. Brenner DR, Tammemägi MC, Bull SB, Pinnaduwa D, Andrulis IL. Using cancer registry data: agreement in cause-of-death data between the Ontario Cancer Registry and a longitudinal study of breast cancer patients. *Chronic Dis Can.* 2009;30(1):16-19.
35. Hanley GE, Morgan S. On the validity of area-based income measures to proxy household income. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2008;8(1):1-7. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-8-79/TABLES/5